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3 **CORRELATIONS BETWEEN SOIL SODICITY AND FOLIAR SYMPTOM OF**
4 **WOOD DECAY OF KIWIFRUIT**

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13 **Running title:** Soil sodicity correlates with kiwifruit wood-decay

14

15 **SUMMARY**

16

17 Wood decay of kiwifruit (*Actinidia deliciosa*) is a relatively new disease of complex etiology. This disease
18 has gained much attention in recent years because it has become wide-spread in kiwifruit-growing areas. Foliar
19 symptoms of the disease are associated with toxins produced by pathogens and develop presumably in response
20 to certain environmental and physiological factors. Vineyard surveys were conducted over nine years in a main
21 Italian kiwifruit growing area, to investigate a potential correlation between soil sodicity and the occurrence of
22 leaf symptoms. Greenhouse trials were also carried out to evaluate physiological parameters potentially
23 associated with the symptom, as the transpiration rate, the stomatal conductance, the net photosynthesis, and the
24 water potential of potted vines grown with different levels of soil sodicity. In the vineyard trials, an increase in
25 soil sodicity significantly increased the incidence of wood decay of kiwifruit. Higher levels of soil sodicity
26 correlated to increased transpiration and decreased water potential in plant tissues, which in turn can increase
27 toxin translocation to an accumulation in the leaf.

28

29 *Key words:* *Phaeoacremonium* spp., *Cadophora malorum*, disease incidence, leaf gas exchange,
30 water potential.

31

32 **INTRODUCTION**

33

34 The total yield of kiwifruit world-wide in 2010 was about 1,350,207 tonnes, most of which produced
35 in Italy, New Zealand and Chile (Faostat, 2010). For approximately the last ten years, kiwifruit
36 cultivation has been affected by a number of new fungal wood diseases having a chronic pattern and
37 multiple causes. The first of these diseases was initially recorded in Emilia-Romagna, North-central
38 Italy, and mainly caused extensive decay in the wood of the trunk and cordons, as a result of which it
39 was named “wood decay of kiwifruit” (Di Marco *et al.*, 2000). The disease was later reported in other

40 Italian Regions (Abbatecola *et al.* 2007; Tosi *et al.*, 2008) and in Greece, France, and Chile (Elena and
41 Paplomatas, 2002; Hennion *et al.*, 2003; Auger *et al.*, 2012). No effective control strategies against this
42 type of diseases are available yet, except for, in some cases, trunk renewal practices (Di Marco *et al.*,
43 2003; Calzarano *et al.*, 2004). Recently, similar wood diseases in kiwifruit have also been reported,
44 such as diebacks and elephantiasis in Italy (Riccioni *et al.*, 2007; Prodi *et al.*, 2008), and New Zealand
45 (Johnston *et al.*, 2010).

46 The wood decay of kiwifruit exhibits two types of wood symptom (Di Marco and Osti, 2008). The
47 first type consists in extended areas of white rot, with light-coloured and crumbly wood, from which
48 *Fomitiporia mediterranea* is isolated (Di Marco *et al.*, 2000). The second type of symptom derives
49 from a tracheomycosis and appears as brown spots from which *Phaeoacremonium* spp., and to a less
50 extent *Cadophora malorum* are isolated (Di Marco *et al.*, 2000; 2004). Leaf symptoms are usually first
51 noticed in 8-10-year-old vines (Di Marco *et al.*, 2000); Affected leaves show polygonal necrotic spots
52 that increase in size and coalesce until they cover the leaf blade; when the symptoms are severe the
53 leaves fall prematurely. Leaf symptoms usually appear about one month after full flowering, and then
54 they spread through the kiwifruit vineyard until they reach their maximum extent at the beginning of
55 September (Di Marco and Osti, 2008).

56 The leaf symptoms are the only means to diagnose the disease in the vineyard. As for esca of
57 grapevine, even if a vine is symptomatic one year, it may fail to show symptoms in a subsequent season
58 or seasons, so to appear healthy although infected (Mugnai *et al.*, 1999; Marchi *et al.*, 2006; Di Marco
59 and Osti, 2008). For that reason the incidence of the disease assessed in only one season will seem
60 lower than it really is. Only a careful inspection of the vines every year over a number of years can lead
61 to a true estimate of the incidence and the severity of the disease (Di Marco and Osti, 2008).

62 Recent studies seem to indicate that there is a correlation between the yield and quality of the kiwi
63 fruit produced and leaf symptoms (Di Marco *et al.*, 2003; Osti *et al.*, 2007). Understanding the causes

64 of the leaf symptoms, in order to influence their expression, is therefore important as it may not only
65 alleviate the disease in the kiwi vine, but also assist in maintaining the productivity of the stand.

66 The factors that cause the leaf symptoms and that enable them to be intermitted for subsequent
67 seasons have not yet been elucidated. Laboratory assays are being carried out to reproduce symptoms
68 on leaf tissue (Osti et al 2012), but no protocols have been developed so far to artificially reproduce
69 any foliar symptoms on kiwifruit vines. However, some hypotheses can be borrowed from esca of
70 grapevine, which is a very similar disease in terms of the main causal fungi involved, the type of wood
71 deteriorations, and the occasional failure of the leaf symptoms to appear during growing seasons (Di
72 Marco *et al.*, 2000; 2004; Fisher 2006; Di Marco and Osti, 2008; Gramaje *et al.*, 2009). Studies on esca
73 suggest that toxic substances are produced in woody tissues by a similar range of tracheomycotic fungi
74 that also cause wood decay of kiwifruit; these toxic substances are then translocated to the leaves,
75 where they produce the symptoms of esca probably once they reach a certain threshold (Surico *et al.*,
76 2006). The amount of toxins translocated from the trunk to the leaves, and the extent of this
77 translocation may therefore be dependent on factors that determine the xylem flow, and that indirectly
78 also determine foliar symptom (Di Marco and Osti, 2009; Di Marco *et al.*, 2011). The toxic substances
79 produced by tracheomycotic fungi associated with the wood decay of kiwifruit are now also in the
80 process of being identified and tested on leaf tissue (Osti *et al.*, 2012).

81 The dependence of xylem flow on seasonal weather conditions would then explain at least in part
82 why symptoms sometimes fail to appear in a season (Marchi *et al.*, 2006; Surico *et al.*, 2006). With
83 kiwifruit for instance it has been established that the manifestation of the foliar symptoms of wood
84 decay is correlated with the temperature from June to August (Di Marco and Osti, 2008).

85 A study examining the relation between kiwifruit wood decay and soil parameters such as pH, active
86 lime, total nitrogen, available phosphorus, exchangeable potassium or soil structure, found no relation
87 between the disease and any of these variables. Only the use of fertiliser based on iron chelate was

88 slightly correlated with a decrease of the incidence of the disease in the vineyard (Di Marco and Osti
89 2008; Osti and Di Marco, 2008); it could be hypothesized that the fertiliser activated the causal fungi to
90 produce non-enzymatic mechanisms associated with the production of hydroxyl radicals, that somehow
91 protected the plants by inactivating fungal toxins (Osti and Di Marco, 2010). However, further data
92 from preliminary vineyard investigations showed that the amount of sodium in the soil seemed to be
93 related to the foliar symptoms of the wood decay of kiwifruit (Osti and Di Marco 2011).

94 In the present work reported on correlations between soil sodicity and both incidence of the disease
95 in the field, and, on potted vines, physiological parameters associated with the leaf symptom
96 appearance.

97

98 **MATERIALS AND METHODS**

99

100 **Selection of vineyards.** Vineyard inspections were carried out in 2003 on 60 vineyards of kiwi cv.
101 Hayward. Vineyards were located in a main kiwifruit-growing area comprising a plain and the foothills
102 of the province of Ravenna, and to a less extent, of Forli-Cesena, in Emilia-Romagna, north-central
103 Italy (Fig. 1). All vineyards were established with kiwi trained to the T-bar system and ranging in age
104 from 8 to 24 years.

105 Five of these vineyards located and identified as Casale, Fregiolo, Formellino, Santa Lucia-1 and
106 Santa Lucia-2 were selected in 2003 for further monitoring; they were as much as homogeneous as
107 possible as to age (9-10 years), prevailing weather conditions, and agricultural practices used, but they
108 differed in soil sodicity, with values covering the range of the sodicity values recorded in the area.

109 These vineyards were monitored every year from 2003 to 2011 inclusive, to determine the spread of
110 the disease. Each year, 132 to 242 vines growing in 3 to 5 rows were inspected, depending on the
111 vineyard.

112

113 **Evaluation of leaf symptoms and calculation of the annual and cumulative disease incidence.**

114 About one hundred kiwi vines in each of the 60 vineyards were visually inspected in 2003 at the time
115 of maximum leaf symptom expression, at the last ten days of August, 90-110 days after full blooming
116 (DAFB). Vines were considered symptomatic if they presented at least two symptomatic leaves on one
117 producing shoot (Di Marco and Osti, 2008).

118 The five selected vineyards were monitored annually from 2003 to 2011. The annual disease
119 incidence of each vineyard was calculated as the number of symptomatic vines monitored that year,
120 and expressed as a percentage of the vines inspected. For each vineyard, to determine the cumulative
121 incidence each year, all inspected vines that were symptomatic that year were added to all
122 asymptomatic vines that had been symptomatic in at least one previous year (Marchi *et al.*, 2006; Di
123 Marco and Osti, 2008), and expressed as a percentage of all the vines monitored that year.

124

125 **Vineyard: determination of soil parameters. Soil sodicity indices (exchangeable sodium,**
126 **exchangeable sodium percentage and sodium adsorption ratio) and sodium in the irrigation**
127 **water.** In each of the sixty vineyards the following soil sodicity indices were determined: exchangeable
128 sodium, exchangeable sodium percentage (ESP), and sodium adsorption ratio (SAR). In 2003, about
129 seven DAFB, soil samples were taken from all the vineyards. Three soil samples per vineyard, each
130 representing one replicate and consisting of about 1 litre of soil, were removed from three points at a
131 depth of about 50 cm, each sampling point being at least 20 cm away from a dripper.

132 The soil samples were analysed by measuring the exchangeable sodium, exchangeable calcium,
133 exchangeable magnesium and cationic exchange capacity (CEC). All variables were measured by the
134 barium chloride/ammonium acetate method following standard procedures (Anonymous, 1992).

135 The concentration of individual minerals and the CEC in the soil were calculated as meq kg^{-1} and

136 was used to calculate ESP and SAR as described below and expressed as percentage and $\text{meq}^{0.5} \text{kg}^{-0.5}$
137 respectively:

$$138 \quad \text{ESP} = 100 \frac{[Na^+]}{CEC} \quad \text{SAR} = \frac{[Na^+]}{\sqrt{\frac{[Ca^{2+}] + [Mg^{2+}]}{2}}}$$

139 Soil sodicity of the five vineyards was analysed in 2003, 2007 and 2011 as above described, taking
140 care to collect soil from the beginning, the middle, and the end of the first, the mid and last row
141 respectively. In order to confirm that sodicity alone is one the key differential characteristics, pH, total
142 carbonates, active lime, organic substance, total nitrogen, available phosphorus, exchangeable
143 potassium, sand silt, and clay were also determined in the same soil samples used for sodicity analysis,
144 following the procedures described in Di Marco and Osti (2008).

145 In 2003, 2007 and 2011 three aliquots, each containing 500 ml irrigation water and representing one
146 repetition, were collected from each of the five vineyards. The aliquots were collected from three
147 drippers spread throughout the vineyard.

148 The irrigation water was acidified in the laboratory with nitric acid and analysed by inductively
149 coupled plasma-optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES) as with the leaves described below. The
150 results were expressed as $\text{meq exchangeable sodium l}^{-1}$.

151

152 **Vineyard: correlation between soil sodicity indices and annual or cumulative disease**
153 **incidence.** In 2003, the linear correlation between the exchangeable sodium, SAR or ESP in the soil of
154 each of the 60 vineyards, and the disease incidence was determined.

155 For each of the five selected vineyards, each sodicity index was the average of the values recorded
156 at 2003, 2007 and 2011. For each year of survey, a linear correlation was looked for between these
157 averages for each vineyard and the annual or the cumulative incidence of that vineyard.

158

159 **Selected vineyards: determination of sodium in the leaf.** In 2007, from each of the 5 vineyards
160 ten symptomatic, fully expanded leaves with similar size and sun exposure were collected at 30, 60 and
161 90 DAFB, from the distal portion of shoots of at least 3 vines. Asymptomatic leaves are collected with
162 the same criteria from asymptomatic vines that grew nearby the sampled symptomatic ones.

163 The leaves were stored at -80°C until use. In the laboratory the leaves were ground, mixed with
164 concentrated nitric acid and heated to complete digestion. The amount of sodium was determined by
165 ICP-OES with a JY-24 ICP emission spectrometer (Jobin-Yvon, Grasbrunn, Germany) having the
166 following features: power supplied by a 40.68-MHz generator (model JY 2300), sequential
167 monochromator with a 640-mm focal length equipped with a highly dispersive holographic grating
168 (2400 grooves/mm). Results are expressed as $\mu\text{mole sodium kg}^{-1}$ of leaf fresh weight.

169

170 **Potted vines: soil, vine material, and growing conditions.** Soil for the potted trials was taken in
171 2010 from the three vineyards that had recorded the lowest (Casale, 2.22 meq kg^{-1}), the intermediate
172 (Formellino, 3.09-3.26 meq kg^{-1}), and the highest (Santa Lucia-2, 5.35-5.91 meq kg^{-1}) sodium levels in
173 the soil analyses of 2003 and 2007. From each vineyard a total of about 150 litres of soil was removed
174 from 3 points in the same manner and dates as the soil that was removed for the determination of soil
175 sodicity indices, as described above. The soil from each vineyard was mixed and homogenised with a
176 mechanical hoe, and placed in 10 pots with a capacity of 10 l. each. One two-year-old kiwi cv.
177 Hayward clone 8 (Ferguson, 1999) obtained by micropropagation, and previously grown in peat, sand
178 and sterile soil (50:20:30), was planted in each pot. The potted vines were placed randomly in three
179 rows, in the open air, but protected in summer by 60% shade netting. From May to September vines
180 were watered with tap water (1.01 meq exchangeable sodium l^{-1}). A total of 4 litres per vine were
181 supplied daily. Plants were irrigated twice a day for 30 min each by means of self-regulating drippers
182 by a programmed centralised watering system model Miracle 6 DC (Netafim, Tel Aviv, Israel).

183

184 **Potted vines: analysis of gas exchange.** Five potted vines grown either in low, intermediate or high
185 soil sodicity were tested; the gas exchange was measured on three leaves per potted vine, each leaf
186 representing one replicate, in each year of the trial. Leaves used for testing grew on the same position
187 of the shoot and had the same size and appearance.

188 Gas exchange was determined in the first week of July 2010 and 2011, using a portable ADC LCA3
189 (Analytical Development Co.) equipped with an infra-red cuvette and a Parkinson leaf chamber to
190 collect the gas exchanged from a leaf surface of 6.2 cm². The measurements were taken from 1 p.m to 4
191 p.m., when photosynthetic activity was most stable (Greaves and Buwalda, 1996). The data are
192 expressed as $\mu\text{mole CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for net photosynthesis, $\text{mmole H}_2\text{O m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for the transpiration rate,
193 and $\text{mol H}_2\text{O m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for stomatal conductance.

194

195 **Potted vines: analysis of water potential.** The water potential of the leaf and stem of vines grown
196 in soil with the different levels of sodicity was determined in September 2010 and 2011 on groups of
197 four potted vines, each group grown in soil with one of the tested sodicity. One leaf was selected from
198 each vine in each group to determine the leaf water potential of that group, and one leaf was taken from
199 near the trunk to measure the water potential of the trunk. Each leaf represented one replicate.

200 To determine the leaf water potential, the leaf was wrapped in a sheet of aluminium foil,
201 immediately after which the leaf was detached, uncovered, and the water potential was measured in a
202 Scholander pressure chamber following the method by Morandi *et al.* (2010). The leaf selected for the
203 measurement of stem water potential was treated in the same way as above, except that it was kept
204 wrapped up in aluminium foil for 2 hours. The values of leaf and stem water potential are expressed in
205 bar.

206

207 **Statistical analysis.** Annual or cumulative incidence was compared each year among the vineyards
208 at different soil sodicity using chi-square statistical analysis at $P = 0.001$.

209 For each vineyard and date of sampling, the content of sodium in the leaf collected from
210 symptomatic and asymptomatic vines was compared with Student's t test at $P = 0.05$. Leaf sodium
211 content of symptomatic or asymptomatic vines among vineyards or sampling dates, water sodicity and
212 soil parameters among years or vineyards, were compared with analysis of variance (ANOVA) at $P =$
213 0.05 . Tukey's multiple range test ($P = 0.05$) was performed to compare soil sodicity among the five
214 selected vineyards, and transpiration rate, stomatal conductance, net photosynthesis, leaf and stem
215 water potential of potted vines grown at low, intermediate or high soil sodicity.

216 Correlations between annual or cumulative disease incidence and soil sodicity indices were analysed
217 by linear regression at $P = 0.05$, and simple Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) was determined.

218 All statistical analyses were performed using SAS system software, Version 9.1 (SAS Institute,
219 Cary, NC, USA).

220

221 **RESULTS**

222

223 **Sixty vineyards: determination of soil sodicity indices, annual disease incidence, and**
224 **correlations analysis.** The exchangeable sodium, ESP and SAR, and the annual disease incidence of
225 the sixty fields for 2003 are shown in Figure 2. The lowest values of exchangeable sodium, ESP and
226 SAR were 1.04 meq kg^{-1} , 0.463% and $0.235 \text{ meq}^{0.5} \text{ kg}^{-0.5}$ respectively, and the highest values were 5.35
227 meq kg^{-1} , 3.04% and $1.11 \text{ meq}^{0.5} \text{ kg}^{-0.5}$ respectively. Contrasting with these differences, the annual
228 disease incidence varied much more, from 0.83% to 58% .

229 A correlation between annual incidence and each of the inspected sodicity indices was found,
230 showing that higher levels of sodicity had a higher annual disease incidence (Fig. 2).

231

232 **Selected vineyards: determination of annual and cumulative disease incidence.** The incidence
233 of symptomatic vines in the five inspected vineyards varied from year to year. However, it was possible
234 to statistically identify ($P < 0.001$) three groups of vineyards for annual incidence (Table 1). These
235 showed low values (0.6 - 4.2%) in the first group, Casale and Fregiolo; intermediate values (11.2 -
236 29.8%) in Formellino vineyard and high values (19 - 48.65%) in the third group, Santa Lucia-1 and
237 Santa Lucia-2. Two exceptions were observed in 2004, when the intermediate vineyard Formellino
238 was lower than, but statistically similar to one vineyard with high annual incidence (Santa Lucia-1);
239 and in 2008 when the intermediate vineyard Formellino was lower but statistically similar to both
240 vineyards with high annual incidence, Santa Lucia-1 and Santa Lucia-2 (Table 1).

241 The cumulative disease incidence of these five vineyards clearly statistically ($P < 0.001$) divided
242 them into the same three groups that were described for annual incidence (Table 2).

243

244 **Selected vineyards: determination of soil parameters. Soil sodicity indices (exchangeable**
245 **sodium, exchangeable sodium percentage and sodium adsorption ratio) and sodium in the**
246 **irrigation water.** Data reported in Table 3 show that there were no significant variations among
247 vineyards for each of the measured parameters except for soil sodicity (Table 3). The amount of
248 exchangeable sodium, ESP and SAR in the soil did not statistically vary ($P = 0.05$) from year to year in
249 the vineyards monitored annually. For each soil sodicity parameter three groups of vineyards with low
250 (Casale and Fregiolo), intermediate (Formellino) and high (Santa Lucia-1 and Santa Lucia- 2) soil
251 sodicity were statistically ($P < 0.05$) identified (Tab. 3). The exchangeable sodium in the irrigation
252 water did not vary statistically ($P = 0.05$) among vineyards or years (Table 3).

253

254 **Selected vineyards: correlation between soil sodicity indices and annual or cumulative disease**

255 **incidence.** The correlations shown in Table 4 between the annual disease incidence of each of the five
256 vineyards and their sodium, ESP and SAR average values were always significant ($P < 0.05$), simple
257 (Pearson's) correlation coefficient ranging from 0.924 to 0.992, 0.878 to 0.995, 0.914 to 0.995
258 respectively (Table 4). The correlations between the sodium indices and the cumulative disease
259 incidence were also always significant ($P < 0.05$). Simple (Pearson's) correlation coefficients were
260 always positive therefore indicating that disease incidence increased with increasing sodicity indices
261 (Table 4).

262

263 **Selected vineyards: determination of sodium in the leaf.** The leaf sodium content in a vineyard
264 varied independently of the soil sodicity of that vineyard. In none of the vineyards was there any
265 significant relation between soil sodicity and the sodium content in symptomatic ($65 - 100 \text{ mmol kg}^{-1}$)
266 or asymptomatic ($61 - 98 \text{ mmol kg}^{-1}$) leaves at any of the sampling dates ($P = 0.05$).

267

268 **Potted vines: analysis of gas exchange.** Higher soil sodicity levels significantly increased the leaf
269 transpiration rate in both test years ($P < 0.05$). In 2010, as shown in Figure 3A, vines grown at high soil
270 sodicity showed a transpiration rate of $4.01 \text{ mmol sec}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2}$, which was significantly greater than the
271 transpiration rate of $2.82 \text{ mmol sec}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-1}$ found in vines grown in soil with low sodicity. In 2011, too,
272 the increase in transpiration rate of vines grown at intermediate soil sodicity was significant ($P < 0.05$)
273 compared to what assessed at low soil sodicity (Fig. 3A).

274 The stomatal conductance increased with increasing soil sodicity. This increase was significant for
275 high compared to intermediate and low soil sodicity ($P < 0.05$) in 2010 (Fig. 3B).

276 In both test years net photosynthesis did not vary significantly ($P = 0.05$) with soil sodium levels
277 (Fig. 3C).

278

279 **Potted vines: analysis of water potential.** The value of leaf water potential decreased significantly
280 ($P < 0.05$) with increasing soil sodicity (Fig. 4A). In 2010 the leaf water potential was -6.57 bar in
281 vines grown in low-sodic soil, but only -8.93 in vines grown in high-sodic soil. In 2011 the leaf
282 water potential recorded in the same vines went down from -6.65 bar to -8.9 bar (Fig. 4A).

283 Higher levels of soil sodicity also significantly reduced stem water potential in both 2010 and 2011
284 (Fig. 4B); in 2010 it went from -6.125 to -8.45 bar in vines grown in low sodicity vs high sodicity and
285 in 2011 from -6.25 to -8.6 bar in the same soils.

286 In both years the water potential was greater in the trunk than in the leaves.

287

288 **DISCUSSION**

289

290 The study demonstrates that, on the whole, soil sodicity correlates with leaf symptoms of the wood
291 decay of kiwifruit. The most important finding was that this effect already occurred at soil sodium
292 levels well below the toxicity threshold (Chartzoulakis *et al.*, 1995; Sotiropulos and Dimassi, 2004) in a
293 typical and highly suitable kiwi-growing area, and under optimal growing conditions (Costa *et al.*,
294 1992).

295 The concentration of sodium in the irrigation water did not differ among vineyards or in years of
296 investigation, thus a possible role of the content of sodium in the irrigation water must be ruled out. On
297 the contrary, the positive linear correlation between soil sodicity and both the annual and the
298 cumulative incidence of the disease was clearly demonstrated. Furthermore, since the amount of
299 sodicity in the soil varied only very slightly during the years of the experiment, it can be concluded that
300 the soil sodicity of a vineyard is a factor predisposing to wood decay of kiwifruit foliar symptoms.

301 As regards the mechanism(s) explaining the correlation between soil sodium content and foliar
302 symptoms, the lack of a correlation between the amount of sodium in the soil and the amount of

303 sodium in the leaves throughout the growing season confirms that there is no seasonal pattern for leaf
304 sodium accumulation (Smith *et al.*, 1987), at least for a sodium excluder plant such as kiwi
305 (Chartzoulakis *et al.*, 1995). Since the sodium contents of healthy and symptomatic leaves are broadly
306 similar, and no correlation between soil and leaf sodium levels was found, it can be concluded that leaf
307 sodium levels do not have a direct effect on leaf symptoms.

308 To determine the factors that produce the leaf symptoms, some early studies have already been
309 carried out on kiwi (Di Marco and Osti, 2008, Osti *et al.*, 2012), and an even greater number on esca of
310 grapevine (Petit *et al.*, 2006; Surico *et al.*, 2006; Di Marco and Osti, 2008; Magnin-Robert *et al.*, 2011;
311 Calzarano *et al.*, 2013). These studies suggest that the leaf symptoms are partly dependent on the
312 physiology of the plant, its phenological growth stage, its translocation capability, and its photosystem
313 effectiveness.

314 The current hypothesis for the foliar symptoms occurrence in the wood decay of kiwifruit is the
315 translocation of the toxic substances produced by tracheomycotic fungi to the leaves (Osti *et al.*, 2012).
316 Higher transpiration can lead to an increase in translocation of solutes (i.e. toxins) (Branton and
317 Jacobson, 1962; Siddiqui and Glass, 1987; Mester and Buhler, 1991; Elad *et al.*, 1993; Pilon-Smith *et*
318 *al.*, 1999). Moreover, transpiration separates water from solutes thus accumulating in the leaf (Canny,
319 1995); so an increased transpiration may lead to a higher accumulation and activity of toxins (Bruno *et*
320 *al.*, 2007) favouring the formation of leaf symptoms as already suggested for grapevine esca complex
321 (Mugnai *et al.*, 1999; Surico *et al.*, 2006). Therefore we investigated and discussed whether soil
322 sodicity, even when within agriculturally safe limits, promoted kiwi vine transpiration and
323 consequently the development of leaf symptoms.

324 Physiological parameters were measured under controlled conditions on plants grown in pots, in
325 order to avoid the variables linked to the day-time measurements, that can occur in vineyards located
326 kilometers apart. However, potted plants were grown in the same soils under which the manifestation

327 of symptoms occurred, also in order to reduce the risk of an increase of the effect of sodium on the
328 physiological parameters, increase that can occur in sodium dose-response trials carried out in potted
329 plants (Steduto *et al.*, 2000).

330 The photosynthetic activity rate, as well as the amount of sodium in the leaves remained constant at
331 all tested soil sodicity levels, while transpiration rate increased with increasing soil sodicity, as
332 expected for sodium excluder plants as kiwifruit is (Chartzoulakis *et al.*, 1995), so, the stability of
333 photosynthesis is a further proof that a significant toxicity was not reached, in an agronomical
334 perspective. On the contrary, when the sodicity in the soil increased, the water potential of the stem
335 decreased; probably the plant, as a result of a signal sent from the roots to the stem (He *et al.*, 2004;
336 Navarro *et al.*, 2007), has to react for the greater difficulty of extracting water from the soil (Volkmar *et al.*, 1998). The decrease of stem water potential assessed in this study could give rise to an increase of
337 water uptake. Moreover, the difference between the water potential of the stem and that of the leaves
338 remained the same irrespective of variations in the sodium level, and hence the capability of the water
339 to move from the stem to the leaf remained unvaried (Begg and Turner, 1970). Therefore, this
340 capability can increase with the increase of soil sodicity levels. This hypothesis, combined with the
341 increase of stomatal conductance measured at higher soil sodicity, is in agreement with the increase of
342 transpiration rate that was clearly assessed at higher levels of soil sodicity. Moreover, as already
343 mentioned, the kiwi vine is a sodium excluder plant, retaining in the roots most of the sodium it absorbs
344 from the soil (Chartzoulakis *et al.*, 1995; Munns *et al.*, 2007). Also in other sodium excluder plants such
345 as rice and bean, the retention of sodium with increasing soil sodicity can lead to an increase in
346 transpiration or in stomatal conductance (Naito *et al.*, 1994; Cabot *et al.*, 2009) as assessed for kiwi
347 vines in this study.

349 The decrease of stem and leaf water potential and the greater transpiration with higher levels of
350 sodium in the soil would favour the translocation and the accumulation to the leaves of toxic substances

351 produced by the tracheomycotic pathogens, and increase the likelihood of leaf symptoms appearing,
352 which would result in a greater annual and cumulative incidence of the disease in the vineyard. Such an
353 explanation would be consistent with recent studies on esca of grapevine, which examined whether
354 rainfall or a variety of treatments, by causing variations in the translocation of toxic metabolites to the
355 vines, also had an effect on the leaf symptoms of esca (Marchi et al., 2006; Calzarano et al., 2007; Di
356 Marco and Osti, 2009; Di Marco et al., 2011).

357 It is concluded that the amount of sodium correlates to foliar symptom of wood decay of kiwifruit,
358 whereas leaf sodium content does not seem to affect the symptom development. Increased salinity
359 would then lead to an increase in the incidence of the leaf symptoms of the wood decay of kiwifruit
360 with possible repercussions on the health, yield and life span of kiwi vines in the vineyard. Thus, soil
361 sodicity level could be considered as a promising preventive indicator of wood decay incidence in
362 kiwifruit. To our knowledge, this is the first time that a preventive indicator could be considered for this
363 type of diseases. If the amount of sodium in the soil even at agriculturally safe levels can yet make kiwi
364 vines more susceptible to the disease, this is cause for concern, also because the ongoing climate
365 changes are thought to increase soil salinity (Utset and Borroto, 2001; Meybeck, 2003).

366

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372

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506

507 **Table 1.** Selected vineyards: annual incidence of the wood decay of kiwifruit.

508

Vineyard	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011
Casale	3.9 a ¹	2.5 a	1.9 a	3.3 a	1.2 a	0.6 a	1.3 a	1.9 a	3.3 a
Fregiolo	1.0 a	5.8 a	1.6 a	1.3 a	1.0 a	1.9 a	1.2 a	2.9 a	4.2 a
Formellino	11.2 b	29.8 b	21.0 b	16.1 b	11.2 b	16.1 b	14.1 b	15.1 b	21.5 b
Santa Lucia-1	37.2 c	35.5 b	38.5 c	28.0 c	28.0 c	18.9 b	23.3 c	26.4 c	31.1 c
Santa Lucia-2	29.1 c	48.7 c	43.2 c	25.6 c	28.4 c	20.9 b	28.4 c	30.2 c	33.7 c

509

510 ¹ Values in column followed by the same letter did not differ statistically according to X² ($P < 0.001$).

511

512 **Table 2.** Selected vineyards: cumulative incidence of the wood decay of kiwifruit.

513

Vineyard	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011
Casale	3.9 a ¹	5.8 a	6.4 a	7.6 a	8.5 a	8.5 a	8.3 a	9.1 a	11.6 a
Fregiolo	1.0 a	6.5 a	6.5 a	7.4 a	7.4 a	8.7 a	9.0 a	11.3 a	13.2 a
Formellino	11.2 b	41.0 b	50.7 b	56.6 b	60.0 b	68.8 b	75.1 b	76.1 b	79.0 b
Santa Lucia-1	37.2 c	56.1 c	73.3 c	78.0 c	81.8 c	82.4 c	84.8 c	87.8 c	88.2 c
Santa Lucia-2	29.1 c	60.8 c	74.1 c	80.9 c	82.4 c	82.9 c	83.7 c	84.4 c	87.2 c

514

515 ¹ Values in column followed by the same letter did not differ statistically according to X² ($P < 0.001$).

516 **Table 3.** Exchangeable sodium in the water, soil sodicity indices (exchangeable sodium, exchangeable sodium percentage and sodium adsorption ratio)
 517 and soil parameters of the five selected vineyards.

Parameter/sodicity index	Measurement unit	Year of survey		Vineyard				
		Casale	Fregiolo	Formellino	Santa Lucia-1	Santa Lucia-2		
Water analysis	Exchangeable sodium	(meq l ⁻¹)	2003	7.99 ^{1 2}	7.98	7.95	7.96	7.97
			2007	7.94	7.95	7.94	7.92	7.96
			2011	7.97	7.99	7.97	7.96	7.99
	Acidity/alkalinity degree	pH	2003	7.99	7.98	7.95	7.96	7.97
			2007	7.94	7.95	7.94	7.92	7.96
			2011	7.97	7.99	7.97	7.96	7.99
Soil analysis	Total carbonates	(%)	2003	16.6	15.2	17.7	13.7	14.4
			2007	17.4	14.8	16.3	14.3	15.6
			2011	16.4	15.4	17	14.5	15.2
	Active lime	(%)	2003	7	6.9	6.8	6.6	6.9
			2007	7.3	6.6	6.2	6.8	6.6
			2011	7.1	6.7	6.5	6.6	6.9
Organic substance	(%)	2003	1.54	1.59	1.49	2	1.77	

		2007	1.69	1.44	1.95	1.67	1.45
		2011	1.63	1.56	1.77	1.85	1.49
		2003	0.13	0.11	0.14	0.12	0.12
Total nitrogen	(‰)	2007	0.11	0.12	0.11	0.14	0.13
		2011	0.12	0.13	0.12	0.11	0.14
		2003	0.61	0.81	1.03	0.71	0.74
Available phosphorus	mg kg ⁻¹	2007	0.74	0.87	0.84	0.77	0.87
		2011	0.65	0.73	0.85	0.76	0.74
		2003	6.31	5.3	5.69	5.1	5.62
Exchangeable potassium	(meq kg ⁻¹)	2007	5.69	4.08	6.62	5.72	5.77
		2011	4.78	5.07	5.5	6.11	5.23
		2003	2.22a ³	2.35a	3.09b	4.48c	5.35c
Exchangeable sodium	(meq kg ⁻¹)	2007	2.22a	2.61a	3.26b	5.3c	5.91c
		2011	2.39 ^o	2.74a	4.26b	5.83c	6.57c
		2003	194	176	123	180	171
Exchangeable calcium	(meq kg ⁻¹)	2007	166	172	134	186	181
		2011	152	141.7	166.7	206.1	195.5
		2003	17.4	16.3	16.3	18	15.3
Exchangeable magnesium	(meq kg ⁻¹)	2007	17.1	15.13	18.2	20.7	19.6

		2011	16.6	14.5	20.39	19.94	20.39
		2003	219	199	151	207	211
Cation exchange capacity (CEC)	(meq kg ⁻¹)	2007	188	191	164	215	209
		2011	174	168	217	248	259
		2003	1.01a	1.18a	2.05b	2.16c	2.54c
Exchangeable sodium percentage (ESP)	(%)	2007	1.18a	1.37a	2.00b	2.36c	2.62c
		2011	1.37a	1.63a	1.96b	2.35c	2.54c
		2003	0.216a	0.239a	0.369b	0.45c	0.555c
Sodium adsorption ratio (SAR)	(meq ^{-0.5} kg ^{-0.5})	2007	0.232a	0.27a	0.355b	0.523c	0.586c
		2011	0.261a	0.305a	0.418b	0.536c	0.595c
		2003	20.7	28.2	29.4	23.2	24.1
Sand	(%)	2007	19.3	28.8	29.6	21.6	26.1
		2011	21.1	27.4	29.5	22.4	24.9
		2003	53.3	47.3	51.5	54.2	46.5
Silt	(%)	2007	54.7	45.1	48.5	55	49.3
		2011	53.1	46	48.3	56.4	49.8
		2003	26.6	25.2	20.3	23.7	25.8
Clay	(%)	2007	25.4	26.2	20.7	22.3	28.2
		2011	25.8	26.6	22.2	21.2	25.3

518 ¹ For each parameter or sodicity index, means in the same column did not differ significantly in the period 2003-2011, according to ANOVA ($P =$
519 0.05).

520 ² Means in the same row not followed by letters did not differ significantly according to ANOVA ($P = 0.05$).

521 ³ Means in the row followed by the different letter did not significantly differ according to Tukey's multiple range test ($P = 0.05$).

522 **Table 4.** Selected vineyards: correlation between the average soil sodicity indices such as exchangeable sodium,
 523 exchangeable sodium percentage (ESP), and sodium adsorption ratio (SAR) and the annual or cumulative
 524 disease incidence.

525

Year	Annual incidence			Cumulative incidence		
	Exchangeable sodium	ESP	SAR	Exchangeable sodium	ESP	SAR
2003	0.932 ^a	0.878	0.914	-	-	-
2004	0.960	0.995	0.979	0.955	0.987	0.970
2005	0.987	0.979	0.990	0.951	0.982	0.964
2006	0.950	0.957	0.953	0.948	0.983	0.962
2007	0.985	0.951	0.978	0.939	0.979	0.954
2008	0.924	0.986	0.948	0.908	0.972	0.930
2009	0.986	0.985	0.947	0.883	0.961	0.909
2010	0.992	0.970	0.995	0.883	0.961	0.909
2011	0.967	0.990	0.979	0.881	0.961	0.908

526

527 ^a Simple (Pearson's) correlation coefficients; the regression probability is always significant ($P < 0.05$).

528

529

530 **CAPTIONS FOR FIGURES**

531 Fig. 1. Location of the sixty vineyards that were inspected for disease incidence and analysed for soil
532 sodicity in 2003.

533

534 Fig. 2. Result of regression analysis carried out in 2003 in the sixty vineyards between annual disease
535 incidence and (A) exchangeable sodium, (B) Exchangeable Sodium Percentage (ESP) and (C) Sodium
536 Adsorption Ratio (SAR).

537

538 Fig. 3. Analysis of gas exchange carried in 2010 and 2011 at low, intermediate and high soil sodicity:
539 transpiration rate (A), stomatal conductance (B), and net photosynthesis (C). Data are the average of 15
540 leaves from 5 potted vines. Error bars represent the standard error of the mean. For each physiological
541 parameter and year of investigation, columns with the same letter did not differ significantly according
542 to Tukey's multiple range test ($P = 0.05$).

543

544 Fig. 4. Analysis of water potential carried out in 2010 and 2011 at low (white columns), intermediate
545 (grey columns) and high (black columns) soil sodicity. Data are the average of 4 leaves from 4 potted
546 vines. Error bars represent the standard error of the mean. For each water potential and year of
547 investigation, columns with the same letter did not differ significantly according to Tukey's multiple
548 range test ($P = 0.05$).

549

553

554

